

Development of Karakalpak Literature of the 21st Century

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Abstract: in this article we analyze the very idea of the Karakalpak literature, as well as how it educates each person, while it develops the speech of any person using its traditional methods. With this, we consider what developed in Karakalpak literature in the 21st century.

Keywords: literature of Karakalpakstan, literature, history, tradition, phenomenon, development, stories, epochs.

The Karakalpak literature of the 21st century itself was the beginning of the development of literacy, but also the development of everything, the beginning of the first steps in the formation of education, views. Basically, in those days, they developed education including their traditions. Due to the fact that the Karakalpak people are the people of some of them who prefer their own tradition, not coming from this. But this is a tradition, the nation is all third-party developed because everything develops together in it, for example, education, view, communication, tradition, science and others.

In every literature there is an instructive trait for education. Great educational features are precisely hidden in old stories, epochs, songs and others. Because they are the result in the upbringing and education of each student. T can easily be quickly presented to their children. And of course, in turn, it is easy for students to read them and understand the very essence of these stories, what others say there.

K. made a great contribution to the development of literature and art of Karakalpakstan . Avezov (1897-1938), famous public figure, writer. The great public work of K. Avezov combined with creative. About the author of historical works "About the events of 1916 in Chennai", "Karakalpakstan to the 10th anniversary of Kazakhstan", "Culture of Karakalpakstan on the path of prosperity and growth". In the 20-30s, his poems "On re-election", "Labor", "Spring", "Cotton", "Sun", poems "Begzhan", "Kazu", "Gulsanem" were popular.

The features uniting the poetic handwriting of Omar- shair, S.Mazhitov, A.Otepov, A.Musaev, S.Nurymbetov, A.Begimov, Zh.Aimurzaev, N.Davkaraev and many others, the combination of traditional and innovative in their work. Translation work of S. Mazhitov. The satirical feature of the work of Omar-shair, A.Musayev, S.Nurym- Betov and others. A.Dabylov is a master of psychological lyrics, the nature of his work.

Creative activity of T.Kabulov. Kabulov as one of the gifted poets of Karakalpakstan. T.Kabulov is a translator of the literatures of fraternal peoples. The works of T.Kabulov in the languages of other peoples. Features of the creative manner of fairy tales, poems, ballads, poems by T. Kabulov. Kabulov as a songwriter. His collaboration with Karakal-Pak composers.

The poem of J.Aimurzayeva "Struggle". The author in this poem is a much more mature artist. The poem is dedicated to the native land, pictures of nature, the work of ordinary people, new trends in the life of the people. The images of Tolepbergen and Torenizyaz, who do not want to put up with a new life, are outlined in bright colors. Karakalpak criticism of those years noted the

author's luck in portraying the positive hero of the poem Karabai. Despite the undeniable advantages, this poem was also not without flaws. This, in particular, refers to the modeling of Bisenbayev's image, which is weakly, declaratively presented.

Tulepbergen Kaipbergenov is one of the leading Karakalpak prose writers. His novels "The Daughter of Karakalpak" and "The Tale of Maman - bey" were a significant contribution to the development of modern Karakalpak literature. The writer's works have been translated into Russian and other languages many times.

The first major work is the novel "The Secretary". It is based on the writer's life experience. Its content is simple - it is a story about the war years in the Karakalpak aul. The author reflected the patriotic work of teenagers, their civic maturity, the growth of self-awareness.

"Thanks to the teacher" - "one of the best works of modern Karakalpak, and maybe all of our literature." Nurmukhamedov M. Modern Karakalpak prose. T., 1968, p. 202. It is dedicated to the difficult work of the first teachers for the Karakalpak people, who selflessly fought against illiteracy in rural areas.

The book "The Daughter of Karakalpak". The novel intertwines many events, phenomena of destinies that make up an integral artistic canvas. In the center of the work is the life and fate of Zhumagul Zaripova, she embodies the full-blooded image of the Karakalpak girl.,

The novel "The Tale of Maman - bie" is the conquest of a new creative height, a clear evidence of the maturity of the master. A vivid image of Maman - biy, a glorious patriot and faithful son of the Karakalpak people. In 1771, the second book "The Destitute" was published, it tells about the life of the Khorezm Karakalpaks. This period reflects the fluctuations, the temporary settlement of the feudal aristocracy, reaching out to the Khanate of Khiva, promising her the usual benefits of life at the expense of the oppressed "lower classes".

The third book is "Incomprehensible". In the center of the new work is the image of the national hero Ernazar Alakoz, who led a popular uprising against Khiva. A feudal lord by birth and views, he at the same time, wisely foreseeing the national goals and interests, pursues a policy, the foundations of which are laid by Maman.

Today, Karakalpak literature has entered a new phase of its development. Absorbing the trends of the new era into their work, Karakalpak writers acquaint readers not only with unique samples, but also translate a lot from other literatures into their native language. Her connections with Turkic literatures have been intensifying recently. "Batyr", "Turkmen daughter Narzhan", "On Fire", "Tamara", and "Political Instructor Polatov", "Native Regiment", "Horseman Shamurat", in which if labor achievements are described at the beginning, then at the end they end with the image of military exploits.

For example, in the poem "The Turkmen girl Narzhan" Zh.Aimurzaev tells about women and heroines who worked selflessly in the rear, their unity in the fight against fascists. The poem reveals the grief of a girl who lost her beloved brother at the front. Hatred brings Narzhans to the front.

With this, I want to say that every literature is important in the development of speech, hearing, sight, and is especially needed by children. Because they are the beginning generation of the whole development, that is, our generation. And the Karakalpak literature itself differs from other literatures in its traditionality.

References

1. Kollektiv avtorov. Istoriya karakalpakskoy literatury (s drevneyshix vremen' do 1917 r.) / Xayimbetov A. — Tashkent: FAN, 1994. — 384 p.
2. Mambetov K. Ayemgi turktilles xalıklardin jazba estelikleri xam onyn karakalpak adebiyati kaliplestiruwdegi tutkan ornı // Amudarya. 1973. № 3.
3. Mambetov K. Erte daurdegi karakalpak adebiyati. Nukus : «Bilim», 1992. — 248 p.

4. Mambetov K. XVI—XVII asirlerdegi karakalpak adabiyati // Amudarya. 1974. № 1.
5. Nurmuxammedov M.K. Karakalpak jazba adabiyatiny doreyi haqqynda // Amudarya. 1968. № 6
6. Paxratdinov A., Otemuratov X. XIX asirdyn aqyry XX asirdyn basyndagy karakalpak adabiyati tarixy. Nukus : «Bilim», 1995. — 316 p.
7. Pirnazarov A. «Oguzname» karakalpak xalqyna da ortaq gazyne // UzSSR Ilimler Akademiyasy Karakalpakstan filialyny xabarshysy. 1982. № 3,4.